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Evaluating The Responsiveness of Movement Frameworks in Peri-urban Neighborhoods: A Case Study of Khulna City, Bangladesh.

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ABSTRACT

Rapid urbanization and population growth in major cities like Khulna have led to the significant expansion of peri-urban neighborhoods. This research evaluates the Responsiveness of Movement Frameworks in such areas, focusing specifically on the Atra neighborhood in Khulna, Bangladesh. The study adopts a multidimensional approach by analyzing road network attributes—such as grid patterns, street connectivity, and nodes—against five core urban design criteria: permeability, variety, legibility, robustness, and visual appropriateness. Through a qualitative and observational methodology, the research investigates pedestrian walkability, transport modes, and visual amenities to determine how the physical infrastructure supports human activity. The findings reveal a significant gap between urban design ideals and ground reality; according to standard urban design perspectives, the movement framework in Atra is non-responsive. However, the study highlights a crucial socio-spatial phenomenon: residents have successfully adapted their lifestyles to this non-responsive environment, maintaining a level of subjective satisfaction. This research provides critical insights for urban planners and policymakers to bridge the gap between technical infrastructure design and the lived experiences of peri-urban communities.

Keywords: Peri-urban Development, Movement Framework, Responsive Environments, Urban Design, Khulna City, Pedestrian Walkability, Spatial Adjustment etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

The share of urban population in the world is increasing day by day. Some countries have more urban population than the rural population. It is seen that 55% of the world's population lives in urban areas, a proportion that is expected to increase to 68% by 2050 (UN, 2018). Projections show that urbanization, the gradual shift in residence of the human population from rural to urban areas, combined with the overall growth of the world's population could add another 2.5 billion people to urban areas by 2050, with close to 90% of this increase taking place in Asia and Africa, according to a new United Nations data set. For that reason, the population of periurban area is also increasing day by day and the basic needs of those area are also increased. Bangladesh is one of the most populated countries in the world. It is anticipated that the country's share of urban population will reach in 56% in 2050 which was 35.8% in 2017 (SHLC report, 2019). Concentration of urban population is increasing rapidly mainly in big cities. In every 1000 people, rural to urban migration was 222.9 in 2011, comparing rural-rural migration was 52.6% and urban-urban migration was 44.4% (SHLC report, 2019). Khulna is a divisional headquarter of Southern Bangladesh. It is the county's first industrial city and the drive of industrialization led an influence of migration of workers towards Khulna City (SHLC report, 2019).

At present the people from other areas are coming towards Khulna City for the sake of employment. For that reason, the population of Khulna city is rising day by day. Periurban growth often are spontaneous and motivated by the need of the shelters. But there is limited work to look at how they are responsive. As The movement framework concerns the structural aspects of movement, focusing on the street and footpath networks (Llewelyn-Davies, 2000), it is a matter of great challenge for the periurban area as the population is increasing day by day and the need of movement framework is rising in that area. Llewelyn-Davies, (2000) maintains that a successful movement framework can be achieved by maximizing the scope of the people of taking their journeys; taking into account of what kinds of movement will generate; and ensuring a clear connection between existing roads and facilities. Llewelyn-Davies, (2000) mentions in the urban design compendium that movement framework consists of four elements, they are: movement assessment which includes quality of the road, air quality, cycle facilities, road safety, trips without delay, walking facilities, pedestrian crossing, noise and pollution, variation in visual amenity, designed area for walkers and cyclists, speed of the transport modes and severance; the walkable neighborhood which is motivated by environmental, health, economic, and communitarian goals; street network which indicates the connections of a road network; and the types of the grid which offers opportunities for traffic management, allowing restriction of car access in some streets.

There are some literatures that tries to focus on the various elements of movement framework. But no literature focuses on the movement framework of periurban area. Some literature focuses on the only a few elements of movement framework for example walkability, permeability, legibility (Anjum, 2016; Hridoy, 2016; Mallick, 2017). Some others try to find out the street design and accessibility, connectivity, pedestrian network or road safety (Song and Knaap, 2004; Cjon-Neil-Corti-Knuiman, 2008; Chataway-Kaplan-Nielsen-Prato, 2014). Those all are the elements of movement framework. Very few literature concerns on urban design perception for identifying movement framework and focuses on the periurban area in this perspective is very little.

This paper is about to explore the condition of existing movement framework in unplanned periurban Atra Neighborhoods of Khulna City and to recognize the responsiveness of this movement framework on this Neighbourhood.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A Movement Framework focuses on the broader structural/aspects of movement as well as more detailed considerations on footpath and road networks (Llewelyn Davies, 2000). On the other hand, when the movement framework is able to enrich the opportunities by maximizing the degree of choice available to people, then that will be called as responsive movement framework. Movement framework has an effect on the degree to which transportation networks such as streets, walking and cycling paths, connect people to their destinations (including intermediate destinations such as public transport services). It provides an easy access to key destinations for pedestrians and seeks to discourage car use by making local trips easier and more pleasant by foot than by car. There are some aspects that are included into movement framework. Llewelyn-Davies, 2000 put forwards number of criteria that can be used to analyze the responsiveness of movement framework. They are: Movement Pattern, Street Network, Walkability within the Neighborhood and Grid. This will form the basis for improving the existing network or creating a new street pattern. Some of the factors to consider in relation to the various modes of transportation (walking, cycling, bus, car, etc.) include: Road safety, links, Nodes, Segregated Path, Transport Modes, Pedestrian Crossing, well connected roads, Visual Amenity, Sidewalks, Bus Stop, Vehicle Speed etc. According to Llewelyn-Davies, 2000 the quality of different routes can be rated to help decide which should be developed or where improvements are needed. Llewelyn-Davies, 2000 mention on their 'Urban Design Compendium' that direct, attractive connections between key facilities, avoiding dead ends, help to create more convenient and comfortable places. An assessment of how best the site can plug into the wider movement networks should aim to provide the maximum number of direct connections to main streets carrying through traffic. He also claimed that the time-honored way of achieving efficient connections is to create a grid, which provides a simple structure, allowing access throughout the area. The form may be orthogonal or more irregular; but its virtues are the same. The grid also offers opportunities for traffic management, allowing restriction of car access in some streets. According to Southworth and Owens, 1993 streets and grid pattern are very important elements for movement framework and streets are responsible for connecting and dividing urban space. The walkable neighborhood offers safe and well functioned neighborhood. When streets, sidewalks and paths (pedestrian routes) are comfortable and interesting, it creates an explicit walking environment (Speck 2012). In Movement Framework, Bicycle is also responsible for creating movement pattern. Walking is very comfortable transport mode but cycling can make the street network more attractive (Zacharias, 2002). Road safety can be ensured by organizing different steams of traffic for example simplifying intersections, dedicated lane for traffic etc. (New York City, Department of Transportation, 2012).

When it comes to the Periurban Movement Framework, the planning procedure in periurban are is developed through incremental and haphazard manner (Journal of the American Planning Association, 1993). The elements of movement framework are insufficient in periurban area. Periurban areas have a lack of pedestrian facilities (Southworth, 2005) Walkable neighborhood is also a matter of challenge in periurban area. Walkable neighborhood in every district of periurban area is need to be assessed (Southworth, 2003). Concentration of urban population is increasing rapidly mainly in big cities. In every 1000 people, rural to urban migration was 222.9 in 2011 (SHLC report, 2018).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Responsive is an urban design term. Bentley mentioned his book 'Responsive Environment' that when built environment should provide its users with an essentially democratic setting, enriching their opportunities by maximizing the degree of choice available to them, then the place will be called as 'responsive'. According to Bentley (1985) there are seven design principle for a responsive build environment. They are permeability, variety, legibility robustness, visual appropriateness, richness and personalization. Where permeability means a place which is more accessible; variety means a place with a lot of uses; legibility which incorporates logical connection between numerous uses; robustness provides public spaces and sidewalks with active edges; visual appropriateness adds an aesthetic quality; richness can give users a multiple experience through different scene; and the place which is more personalized, that is more private place. But those seven principles described by Bentley are more feasible for urban structure. In considering, movement framework, five principles can fulfill its criteria. They are: Permeability, Variety, Legibility, Robustness, and visual Appropriateness. When a movement framework fulfills those characteristics of responsive environment that will be called as 'responsive movement framework'. But richness and personalization is not considered in responsive periurban movement framework as they give detail consideration on urban structure rather than movement quality. As periurban neighborhoods are the ground for urban sprawl, so the responsiveness of movement framework in periurban neighborhood is very much important to consider.

Conceptual Framework

3. STUDY AREA

Atra Area is situated in Atra Gilatola Union. Atra is mainly an industrial area. In here, some key industries especially jute mills area situated. According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), the total number of households in Atra area is 1484. And the total number of populations is 5697. As the population is rising day by day, the movement framework on that area is becoming more interesting. Atra is situated outside of the city corporation area.

Figure 1: Google map view of Study Area

4. METHODOLOGY

The method of this research is mixed research method. Both qualitative and quantitative data is used. Qualitative methods normally deal with the non-numeric data. This research is conducted with deductive approach. In deductive research approach, information is collected from the existing theory. In this approach, the researchers conduct a huge study and find what others have done in his field of interest. Five methods for data collection is used in this research. They are:

4.1 Questionnaire Survey

In this research, questionnaire is mainly closed ended questions. This survey intends to know the perception of movement framework on the basis of urban design criteria. The number of households of Atra area is used for conducting the survey. The sample size is ascertained by the following equation of Taro Yamane elementary sampling techniques:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

Here,

N = Number of households = 1484

n = Sample size

e = error margin

So, for 10% error margin, the sample size will be,

$$n = 1484 / (1 + (1484 \times 0.12)^2)$$

$$n = 94$$

So, 94 is the requiring sample size for this study at the household level survey.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.2 Visual Analysis

In this research, visual analysis plays an important role for data analysis. The four urban design criteria (variety, legibility, visual appropriateness, and robustness) is analyzed through visual analysis in this research. The movement framework criteria that will be analyzed through visual analysis are:

- Segregated Path
- Transport modes
- Movement Pattern
- Nodes
- Road Links
- Road Safety
- Visual Amenity
- Sidewalks and
- Bus stops

4.3 Pedestrian Count Survey

Pedestrian count survey is a very important techniques for measuring the pedestrian flow and also PCU. The number of in and out flow are recorded in a pick hour of a day. Normally a 15 minutes interval is needed for the pedestrian count survey of an hour. In this research the pick hour 10 a.m. to 11 a.m. and 5 p.m. to 6 p.m. Where survey was conducted considering a 15 minutes interval. After counting the pedestrian, the PCU is generated were,

PCU = PCE × Pedestrian flow (in and out)

Here,

PCE = Passenger Car equivalent

for pedestrians PCE = 0.12

PCU = Passenger Car Unit

Pedestrian count survey is done through the two major intersections of Atra neighbourhood. They are: Afil gate intersection and eastern gate intersection. The survey is done considering two different peak hours of a day.

4.4 Walk Through analysis

Walk though analysis mainly used in measuring the visual concerns of an assessment. Various important analysis is showed through photographs or other measures through this analysis. Location of various roads, links, nodes or dead ends is measured through GPS data in this research. For that purpose, google my map is used for ensuring the accuracy of the analysis. Various locations are pointed out through the GPS data in this analysis

5. DATA FINDINGS

Data findings are divided into five different perspectives. They are permeability, variety, legibility, robustness, and visual appropriateness.

5.1 Findings on Permeability

Permeability is an important measure to understand the responsiveness of movement framework because it can describe how urban form restrict or permit people or vehicle to move on a definite direction. Though the permeability of Atra neighborhood is not as good as its ideal attribute

5.1.1 Walkability

From the questionnaire survey, it is seen that most people work for work purposes. It is seen that, the people of Atra neighbourhood prefer walking for their daily purposes or work. About 22% people walk for working purpose and they are mainly labor who are working mainly in jute mills, 20% walk for business purposes. On the other hand, the less amount for walking is the office purposes.

PERCENTAGE OF THE WALKING PURPOSE

Relating gender with walking purposes, it is seen that female walk more than male in shopping and health purposes. On the other hand, male walk more than female in office, recreation, business, work and study purposes.

Walking Purpose

It is seen that most of the people walk which is mainly 8 to 10 minutes distance. It is because the maximum service and facilities area situated between 8 to 10 minutes distance. People tend to walk and reach their destination which is situated near from their residents.

Very few persons walk to avoid congestion and because of low rate of accident. The roads of Atra neighbourhood have a very little rate of traffic congestion. So maximum preference is for saving cost.

Walking Preference

On the other hand, after analyzing gender wise walking preference, it is seen than maximum female prefer walking just to keep healthy and fit. Then female prefer cost savings for walking. But the priority of walking for male is cost saving.

WALKING PREFERENCE

After that a good number of male walk because most of the facilities are situated near to the walking distance.

Problems Associated with walking:

Most of the people claimed that the walking road is damaged. About 46.8% claimed this. On the other hand, 43.6% people are not satisfied because there is no footpath in this area.

Figure 3: Damaged road

Figure 4: No footpath

Figure 2: Poor connection towards residents

5.1.2 Grid pattern

The grid pattern of Atra neighborhood is not in ideal pattern. The grids are scattered and not in well structure. Grid pattern is the good factor for analyzing the pattern of the road network. As the grids are not in well structured, the road network is also not in good structured.

Figure 5: Grid pattern

5.1.3 Pedestrian flow in major roads in Atra neighbourhood

The pedestrian flow of eastern gate intersection is higher than the Afil gate Intersection because there is a big jute mill near Eastern gate intersection. People mainly use carriageway for walking because there is no footpath on that area.

Figure 6: PCU at peak hour

5.1.4 Pedestrian Crossing

There is no pedestrian crossing in Atra neighbourhood. People of this neighbourhood claim that it would be very helpful for them if there can be established a pedestrian crossing in this area. Though there is no pedestrian crossing in this neighbourhood, 56.4% residents cross the road 2 to 3 times daily.

Percentage of crossing road (Daily)

Figure 7: percentage of crossing road

The people of Atra neighbourhood faces some problems during crossing the road. In Atra neighbourhood, there is a lack of street light which is a great problem. 51.1% say that lack of street light is a great problem for them.

Problems during Pedestrian Crossing

Figure 8: Problems in pedestrian crossing

5.2 Variety in Atra Neighbourhood

Variety offers a range of choices and advantages to the people. In the context of movement framework transport modes, segregated path and movement pattern offers a range of choices to the residents.

5.2.1 Transport Modes

Various transport modes offer a good level of choice to the residents of Atra neighbourhood. 83% of the total respondents use Mahindra for travelling one place to another. Mainly Mahindra is the most common transport mode of Atra neighbourhood.

Figure 9: Available Transport Modes

There are so many advantages in transport modes. 80.9% claimed that there is a availability of transport. 12.8% people said there is low gathering in terms of transport modes. Other claimed that there is low rate of traffic congestion. So, transport modes offer various advantages to the people. modes. Other claimed that there is low rate of traffic congestion. So, transport modes offer various advantages to the people.

Figure 10: Advantage of transport modes

39.4% people claimed that the visibility is poor at night means there is a lack of street light which hinders the movements of vehicles and people. On the other hand, 45.7% claimed there is no separate path for pedestrian. There is also risky high speed which is claimed by 12.8% and others include the problem of dead ends. Those are the main disadvantages of transport modes of this area.

Figure 11: Disadvantage of transport modes

5.2.2 Segregated Path

There is no separate path for by cycle, rickshaw and for other vehicles. So in this respect, there is no variety.

Figure 12: No segregated path

5.3 Legibility in Atra Neighbourhood

Legibility helps to make a place with coherent pattern. In movement framework the nodes, condition of dead ends, road links are responsible to make a place coherent or not. So, those are the elements of legibility in movement framework.

5.3.1 Road link

the road links of Atra neighbourhood is good and had a good road link. But the main problem is there are a numerous dead ends in the local roads of this neighbourhood.

Figure 13: Dead ends

5.3.2 Condition of Nodes

From the visual analysis, it is seen that maximum nodes of study area are situated along the main street. But in the local streets, there is a lack of nodes which is a problem for the residents because nodes are an important element for recognizing a place.

Figure 14: Nodes in main streets

5.4 Robustness in Atra Neighbourhood

Robustness offers people offering people more choices than places that have a design that limits them to a single fixed use. It provides public spaces and sidewalks with active edges. In movement framework robustness includes bus stops, sidewalks etc.

5.4.1 Bus Stops

There are three major bus stops which are situated in the Atra neighborhood. Which are enough for them.

Figure 15: Bus stops

5.4.2 Sidewalks

There is a lack of sidewalks in the Atra neighbourhood. In fact, there is no sidewalks in the major roads of Atra neighbourhood. People of this neighbourhood feel trouble while walking on the streets specially in the main street as there is no sidewalks.

Figure 16: No sidewalks

5.5 Visual Appropriateness

Visual appropriateness adds the quality of aesthetic environment. The aesthetic quality of Atra neighbourhood is not bad. There is a branch of trees that are situated around the main road. But in the local street, as maximum roads are damaged, there is a lack of visual amenity. Here, damage roads hampers on visual amenity of local roads but Availability of trees around the street increase the visual amenity along the main street.

Figure 17: Damage road hamper visual amenity

Figure 18: Availability of tree in main street

6. CONCLUSION

Although the neighbourhood is unplanned, people have developed their own movement framework following the basic road networks provided. Theoretically, the neighbourhood is not responsive as basic service and facilities are absent here but People are very adaptive to whatever service is available to them. There is very limited planned intervention as far as Movement Framework is confirmed.

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